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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronyms	Full meaning
BI	Business Intelligence
OEM	Original equipment manufacturer
MLL	Mobility Living Labs
NMS	New and Shared Mobility Services
IDS-RAM	International Data Space Reference Architecture Model

MVDS	Minimum Viable Data Space
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication and trust Services
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connector
TM	TeleManagement
CA	Certified Authority
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
ParIS	Participant Information Service
API	Application Programming Interface
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interface-Linked Data
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
DSBA	Data Space Business Alliance
FI-PPP	Future Internet Public-Private Partnership
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OBD	Onboard Diagnostics
UCs	Use Cases
CAN-BUS	Controller Area Network Bus
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act
AWS	Amazon Web Services
GCP	Google Cloud Provides
OS	Operating System
SSD	Solid State Drive
HTTPS	Hypertext transfer protocol secure
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SSO	Single-Sign-On

CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
CE	Community Edition
SSO	Single Sign On

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This is the first release of two deliverable reports addressing GEMINI Task 4.1, "GEMINI Mobility Data Space and Business Intelligence Platform," which kick-off 6 months ago (M6). The report aims to present the specifications of the GEMINI Data Space and Business Intelligence Platform from both technical and business standpoints.

In more detail, GEMINI Data Space aligns with international data space standards, empowering Mobility Living Labs (MLL) and shared mobility stakeholders with a decentralized and sovereign data sharing mechanism. In addition, the GEMINI Business Intelligence (BI) platform goal is to enable cities and shared mobility providers to leverage shared fleet data in their decision-making and/or operations optimization. In essence GEMINI Data Space and BI platform aim to facilitate project MLL stakeholders and the NMS, they design and will be implemented throughout the project, by providing tools that:

1. Accelerate trusted data sharing among various stakeholders as a key prerequisite for enabling shared mobility.
2. Aggregating diverse mobility data sources (e.g. cars Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), vehicles fleets management, public transportation etc.) and transform them into actionable insights.
3. Foster the creation of fair and trusted models and incentives for data sharing.
4. Maximize interoperability among stakeholders through standardized processes and formats of data sets sharing in the shared mobility ecosystem.

To this end, Chapter 2 begins with a detailed State-of-the-Art analysis, drawing parallels with other initiatives like GAIA-X, International Dataspace Association, etc., so as to leverage best practices for GEMINI Data Space development. Furthermore, Chapter 2 presents Data Space Architecture, core components, and workflows for authentication and authorization of data exchange with the ecosystem. The chapter concludes by outlining GEMINI Minimum Viable Data Space (MVDS) functional requirements, emphasizing the use of open-source software for flexibility and accessibility. Lastly, it describes the identified dataspace UCs for data sharing within the GEMINI MLLs ecosystem and from other public or data marketplaces platform as part of improving the MLLs New Mobility Services offerings.

Chapter 3 described GEMINI Business Intelligence Platform including platform technical infrastructure, features and intelligence needs according to interviews with its intended end-users and finally BI platform analytics and visualization capabilities. In more detail, according to desk research and interviews with MLLs Operators the key areas identified are a) analytics pertaining to pricing and cost strategies, b) user's/drivers behaviour patterns or usage classifications, c) vehicle management (focusing of utilization and repositioning/rebalancing of managed fleet statistics), d) Electric Vehicles (EVs) charging infrastructure and battery

utilization, e) city-level statistic and infrastructure. Furthermore, the report delineates a comprehensive strategy for BI platform architecture and deployment strategies. Finally, the GEMINI Model library and the models currently accessible from the LEAD¹ project are presented as well as the ongoing research and work of developing new models satisfy the above mentions user needs and fostering operational streamlining and efficiency gains across the organization.

In conclusion, this report establishes the cornerstone principles of the GEMINI Data Space and Business Intelligence Platform, aiming to offer the shared mobility community advanced technological solutions. These platforms are designed to effectively manage mobility data, empower data-driven decision-making, and cultivate collaboration among stakeholders within the shared mobility ecosystem.

¹ <https://www.leadproject.eu/>

1 INTRODUCTION

New and shared mobility services are transforming urban mobility and shaping consumer behaviour. In addition, both consumers and service providers increasingly depend on digital means for information exchange between them and the provision of the service, also driven by Information Communications Technology and smart infrastructure advancements. As for example, this may include information in near real time from cars OBU to smart parking and public transport telematics as part of multi modal mobility offerings. This factor emphasizes the need for secure and standardized information exchange among the involved parties. Understanding and addressing the evolving needs of these ecosystems are crucial for sustainable growth of new and shared mobility services.

The key objective of T4.2 is to design GEMINI's infrastructure backbone and digital enablers for new mobility services. This involves developing the GEMINI Mobility data space for secure information exchange and the AI-augmented GEMINI Business Intelligence platform. These tools aim to provide project stakeholders with advanced analytics and data-driven models to optimize operations.

Data Spaces can act as key enabler of shared mobility service since they provide a structured environment for securely sharing data, fostering collaboration, and ensuring interoperability between different systems. By incorporating data spaces decentralized identity mechanisms, GEMINI ensures that data exchange and interactions between stakeholders are conducted maintaining privacy and security standards. This approach not only safeguards sensitive information, inherent of using shared mobility services but also cultivates trust among participants, laying the foundation for collaborative and sustainable mobility solutions. Furthermore, this analysis delved into understanding how these components function within existing data spaces and their potential integration into the GEMINI MVDS.

By leveraging BI tools, operators can optimize resource allocation (both human and capital-related), reduce costs related to the management of the mobility service, and foster more effective collaboration with partners, leading to enhanced quality and sustainability of shared mobility services. Interviews with MLLS partners and fleet managers were carried out to pinpoint key fleet management processes, such as vehicle rebalancing, and to identify relevant assets, information, and analytics crucial for service delivery. Additionally, these interviews served as a platform to discuss and analyse available datasets, their quality, and relevance for GEMINI's Business Intelligence (BI) platform analytics and model development. By aligning with the needs and challenges identified by MLLS partners and fleet managers, GEMINI aimed to develop analytics and models that are both relevant and impactful for optimizing operations and decision-making in the shared mobility landscape.

Finally, the following chapters present findings and insights guiding GEMINI Data Space and BI development.

Deliverable Overview and Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

Chapter 1 introduces the task's objectives and outlines the methodology employed in this report. It sets the stage for the subsequent chapters.

Chapter 2 provides an in-depth exploration of the GEMINI Data Space Architecture, encompassing functionalities, relevant standards, workflows, and application scenarios.

Chapter 3 outlines the GEMINI BI platform, detailing its functional requirements, models, and optimization areas tailored to project end-users. It also highlights key analytics essential for monitoring shared mobility services and achieving project objectives.

Chapter 4 offers the conclusions drawn from this report, alongside a roadmap outlining targets and steps for the forthcoming period.

2 GEMINI DATASPACE

The ever-growing importance of data in today's economy has created challenges around data sharing. Traditional exchange methods, such as email services, shared directories, or free transfer services, often lack security, transparency, and control for data providers. To address these issues, the concept of data space has been introduced in various forms in the last 15 years.

The mobility domain is characterized by its diverse range of data sources, including vehicle telemetry, commuters' data, traffic management systems, and public transit records. The ability to efficiently aggregate, analyse, and exchange this data is essential for optimizing traffic flows, enhancing service offerings, reducing emissions, and improving overall user experiences. However, this exchange must be handled with utmost care to protect user privacy and data integrity. This is where data space fits, by providing a trusted framework that ensures sovereignty of data while enables its controlled exchange.

2.1 Design Principles and international standards

The primary goal of any data space initiative has been the creation of a secure and trusted environment for data sharing while addressing a few important issues, starting with the **Data Sovereignty**. It is imperative for Data Producer entities to maintain control of over the usage of their datasets, while still enabling secure sharing with trusted partners. This is the base for the creation of decentralized data storage infrastructures or even the first steps towards the creation of a data marketplace.

Trust is a paramount prerequisite for a Data Producer to join on such consortiums. This will allow the effective collaboration and innovation in the digital ecosystem. **Security** can be considered as the foundation for building Trust. A data space should provide robust Authentication and Authorization techniques, integrate the latest encryption algorithms, and fine-tuned access management frameworks to safeguard sensitive data both at rest and on the move.

Interoperability is the last significant pillar towards seamless data sharing between multiple businesses and individuals. By defining common standards, protocols, and interfaces facilitate on smooth data flows across disparate systems and platforms. Defining Ontologies and Vocabularies provides additional help by promoting semantic interoperability. These would contribute to improved data discovery and analysis by providing common language for describing

data. This ensures that any data consumer can easily search and discover relevant datasets, understand the meaning of them and identify relationships between data concepts. This concept leads to unlock opportunities for **Innovative** solutions and **value creation** based on available data, that otherwise might remain unexplored and stored on scattered data lakes.

With the introduction of GDPR in EU and similar ruleset such as CCPA, the data sharing methodologies should comply with the **regulatory** requirements to ensure accountability, auditability, and transparency in data processing activities. The data space designs would additionally need to incorporate privacy aware technologies, data governance frameworks and legal rulesets to fully comply with new data protections laws.

Initiatives and State of the Art

The **Big Data Value Association** was the first attempt to define a data space. It was founded in 2014 as the private counterpart of the European Commission in the Big Data Value Public Private Partnership². Its main goal is to promote the adoption of big data and Artificial Intelligence technologies to power the digital transformation across Europe. BDVA has not directly design any data space architecture, but its key principles have heavily influenced data space development.

The **International Data Space Association** is one of the most prominent initiatives. It has been initially conceived as Industrial Data Space by Fraunhofer Society in 2014, before being renamed to IDS in 2015. The IDSA was formed in 2017 to develop the **Reference Architecture Model (RAM)**, currently in version 4, and the certification procedure based on industry requirements³. The association is solely focused on creating a standardized approach to data spaces and to that end it has released a comprehensive set of specifications to define the required schemas, protocols, and interfaces upon which a dataspace is build, named as **Dataspace Protocol**⁴. IDSA also provides resources like the **Data Spaces Radar**⁵ to showcase the adaption of the dataspace approach across different domains. In the GEMINI project, we are following the IDSA Architecture model for designing and implementing the GEMINI Data Space. In the continuation of this report, more information will be given regarding the architecture and implementation of the solution.

GAIA-X⁶ aims to establish a federated and secure data infrastructure, by allowing the stakeholders to retain sovereignty over their data. As a federated service, GAIA-X plan is to link many cloud services providers and user together in a transparent environment that will drive the European Data economy. It has been founded in 2019 as a shared project between German and French Ministries of Economic Affairs. The association provides detailed architecture design, policy and rules guidelines and a Trust framework technical concept.

GAIA-X main building block is the Federation Services, which connects the Infrastructure Ecosystem with the Data Ecosystem. The architecture is based upon Policy Rules and open standards. The goal is the support of a shared economy where a stakeholder can share data and services while maintaining sovereignty over them [1].

² <https://bdva.eu/about/>

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Data_Spaces_Association#History

⁴ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/knowledge-base/dataspace-protocol>

⁵ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/adopt/data-spaces-radar/> and <https://www.dataspaces-radar.org/>

⁶ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

FIWARE⁷ aims to provide a framework of open-source platform components to accelerate the development of smart applications in various domains, including Smart Cities. It originated from the Future Internet Public-Private Partnership (FI-PPP) program, which was a European initiative launched in 2011⁸. The FIWARE Foundation was officially established in 2016 as a non-profit organization[2].

FIWARE provides an open-source development ecosystem that includes a set of standards-based components known as Generic Enablers (GEs). These components offer reusable and commonly needed functions to develop a variety of applications, such as processing, analysis, and visualization of context information, often generated in real-time from IoT devices. NGSI-LD API has been adopted as a standardized API for context information management, that facilitates interoperability and data sharing. In conclusion, FIWARE's primary aim is not to create a dataspace ecosystem, similar to IDSA or GAIA-X, but it does facilitate data exchange through commonly defined interfaces.

Data Space Business Alliance is a collaboration between major European initiatives and organizations aimed at promoting the development and adoption of data spaces across various sectors. Founding members of this alliance include IDSA, GAIA-X, FIWARE and BDVA among others. The alliance was founded in 2021 focusing on promoting the creation, adaptation, and standardization of dataspaces across Europe. To achieve this goal, the alliance has been focused on the technical convergence of existing architectures to define a common reference technology framework and facilitate interoperability, portability of solutions across data spaces, and harmonize technology components among different ecosystems [3].

As part of the implementation driven approach, a Minimum Viable Framework has been developed, based on three major pillars:

- Data Interoperability, which is supported by NGSI-LD API and smart data models, extending interoperability mechanisms with a focus on the IDS-Infomodel and the Vocabulary Hub.
- Data Sovereignty and Trust, which features an eIDAS and EBSI-compatible Trust Anchor framework and a decentralized Identity and Access Management (IAM) framework.
- Data Value Creation through a Centralized Service Catalogue and Marketplace functions which is based on TM Forum standards.

Multiple instances of IDS data spaces have been implemented across various industries. Using the IDS Data Spaces Radar tool, we can access information regarding their specific domains and their levels of maturity. At the time of writing this report, there are eight data space implementations, among which the Mobility Data Space⁹ stands out. This initiative has established a broad network of experts from diverse mobility sectors throughout Europe. Another significant initiative is Mobilithek¹⁰, which is recognized as Germany's largest data source in the mobility sector.

⁷ <https://www.fiware.org/>

⁸ <https://www.fiware.org/2017/03/09/after-the-open-day-from-the-fi-ppp-to-the-fiware-foundation/>

⁹ <https://mobility-dataspace.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://mobilithek.info/about>

2.2 Data Space Reference Architecture Overview

The IDSA dataspace design has been chosen as the base for the GEMINI Data Space. In this subsection we will provide a description of IDSA Architecture known as IDS-RAM¹¹. One of the reasons this was selected was due to fact that there are available technical implementations that can be used for the development of the GEMINI Data Space.

IDS-RAM resides at a higher abstraction level than most common architecture for software solutions. Its focus is to generalize the concept and functionality of a secure 'network of trusted data'. To achieve this, the IDS-RAM uses a five-layer structure for defining the required processes. These five layers are the Business, Functional, Process, Information and System layer.

Business Layer

The business layer focuses on the different roles involved in data exchange, along with their responsibilities and interactions. It identifies the different participants in the data space, such as Data Supplier, Data Consumer, Service Provider, Service Consumer, Metadata Broker and Identity Authority to name the most important for the GEMINI Data Space.

The Business Layer outlines how these roles interact with each other. This includes defining workflows for data discovery, negotiation of data usage terms, and the actual exchange of data. By defining clear roles and expectations, the Business Layer promotes trust and understanding between data providers and consumers. Furthermore, it serves as a blueprint for the technical aspects of the data space. The technical design (defined in other layers) can be verified against the business requirements outlined here.

Functional Layer

The Functional Layer of the IDS-RAM acts as the blueprint for what needs to be achieved in the data space, independent of the specific technologies used. It outlines the essential functionalities required for secure and controlled data exchange.

Figure 1 - IDS RAM Functional Layer

¹¹https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/ids-ram-4/introduction/1_1_goals_of_the_international_data_spaces

Figure 1 - IDS RAM Functional Layer, presents the six groups of functionalities as grouped by the IDS-RAM. The first two groups, "Trust" and "Security & Data Sovereignty" ensure that data is exchanged in a trustworthy and secure manner, while respecting data ownership, privacy regulations and usage policies. Participant Identity through valid certificates is a cornerstone for building this trust in the data space network.

Information Layer

The Information Layer is vital for enabling standardized, (semi-)automated data exchange across a trusted ecosystem. It specifies the Information Model, a domain-agnostic framework serving as a common language or vocabulary for IDS participants, supporting compatibility and interoperability.

The Information Model is presented through three formalization levels, from a high-level conceptual representation down to programmatic representation, ensuring comprehensive understanding and application. Relation to domain-specific vocabularies is essential, with the Information Model allowing for adaptations (Application Profiles) to describe various IDS ecosystem components tailored to specific domains.

Process Layer

The Process Layer outlines how different components interact within the ecosystem, offering a dynamic perspective on the Reference Architecture Model. It encloses processes such as onboarding for Data Providers and Data Consumers to gain access to the IDS, data offering and discovery, contract negotiation focusing on usage policies, data exchange between participants, the publishing and utilization of IDS Apps through the IDS App Store, and the policy enforcement of data usage. These processes are essential to the IDS's core value propositions and engage many of the roles defined in the Business Layer.

System Layer

The System Layer is the technical foundation that supports the secure and interoperable exchange of data within the IDS ecosystem. It outlines the architectural components, protocols, and interfaces necessary for implementing the functionalities and processes described in the upper layers of the IDS-RAM.

Figure 2 - IDS Interaction of technical components.

In the system layer, we may find the definition of the core components of the IDS:

- The Identity Provider, which consists of CA, DAPS and Paris
- The IDS Connector, which is the cornerstone component for any actor to participate in IDS.
- Metadata Broker, which facilitates the data discovery process.
- The Clearing house, for logging any action within the IDS
- The Vocabulary hub for enhancing the interoperability of the data exchange
- The App Store and the Data Apps

In Figure 2 the previously listed components are being depicted along with their main interactions.

2.3 GEMINI Data Space Architecture Desing

Gemini Data Space, as an IDSA compatible data space, is designed on the same principles defined in the IDS-RAM and the Reference Architecture as defined in subsection **Error! Reference source not found.** Based on the IDSA Best Practices Guidelines¹², GEMINI Data Space shall be built upon proven technologies and existing, open-source software components, with focus on achieving a domain independence implementation and low deployment threshold for project partners.

2.3.1 Minimum Viable Data Space¹³

The concept of the MVDS is a best practice approach provided by IDSA, that focuses on establishing a foundational and operational data space with the essential features and

¹²https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/idsa-rulebook/idsa-rulebook/2_guiding_principles

¹³ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/knowledge-base/mvds>

capabilities required to support data discovery and exchange. The concept borrows from the lean startup methodology's idea of a Minimum Viable Product, and emphasizes a quick and cost-effective solution, that introduces the concept to the end users while establishing a feedback loop for future iterations.

GEMINI Data Space follows a similar approach, by deploying an MVDS that will allow project partners to familiarize themselves with the data space concept and offers useful insight to the implementors of the data space.

The technical components that are required for the MVDS are:

- One IDS Connector per Project Partner.
- A Certified Authority (CA) granting X.509 Certificates
- A DAPS

Figure 3 presents the MVDS for GEMINI Project

Figure 3 - Minimum Viable Data Space

Even though the IDS Broker is not a mandatory component of the MVDS, the use of it is of great importance for the GEMINI Data Space in order to promote data discoverability, and therefore it has been included in Figure 3.

Following the iteration approach, additional components are considered to be added to the GEMINI Data Space. An application hub is the first candidate for the next iteration, as it will offer a centralized place to offer data applications for usage by the IDS Connector.

2.3.2 Data Space Software Components

To deploy the Minimum Viable Data Space (MVDS), the decision has been made to utilize open-source software. Specifically, the IDS Connector will be built upon the Eclipse Dataspace Connector¹⁴ (EDC) framework, along with its extension, the Sovity Dataspace Connector¹⁵. The selection of Dataspace Connectors was guided by the IDSA Data Connector Report¹⁶, which catalogues all currently recognized connectors. This decision was informed by their Technology

¹⁴ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/soivity/edc-extensions>

¹⁶ https://internationaldataspace.org/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/IDSA-Data-Connector-Report-5_March-2023.pdf

readiness level (TRL) and the adoption of a non-restrictive license model, ensuring broad usability and flexibility. The Eclipse Dataspace Components are not only scalable and adaptable to various environments but also support a wide array of cloud configurations. Importantly, they are positioned at TRL levels 8-9, indicating that they are fully developed, tested, and validated in real-world environments. The license under which EDC operates is Apache 2.0, which is known for being permissive and business-friendly, ensuring that users can use, modify, and distribute the software with minimal restrictions. Sovity's Dataspace Connector is an extension of EDC offering a robust User Interface and implements a fully functional interface for connecting to API based data sources.

For the Metadata Broker component, two solutions shall be provided. For participants within the GEMINI Data Space, it's necessary to employ IDS-compatible broker software component, such as Sovity's EDC Broker Server¹⁷ that will allow only GEMINI Data Space members to fully take advantage of its search and query features. For non-data space members, it is considered to create a Data Catalogue accessible via a web portal. This catalogue will solely feature metadata about the original data, specifically showcasing data descriptions and keywords without revealing source endpoints or any details that could risk the security of data owners. The goal of this approach to enhance visibility for the GEMINI Data Space.

Regarding the DAPS server, a solution based on Identity Provider software such as Keycloak¹⁸ shall be examined. To establish Trust between data space users, each Partner would get a unique identifier that will be deployed along with the IDS Connector. According to best practices X.509 identity Certificates shall be used. These certificates will either be provided by the IDS Identity Provider CA or through well-known public providers such as Let's Encrypt.

The current implementation of the EDC and Sovity EDC extension allows for direct integration with Rest Servers over API endpoints for Data Sources and Data Sinks. To provide a bigger flexibility for data owners and data consumers, IDS Apps shall be developed that will be able to bridge the gap between the IDS Connectors and different data storages. These Apps shall be deployed as Containers, a method that would provide greater portability for the software delivery, easier scalability if required and better isolation and therefore security. The IDS Apps shall be available either through IDS App store or if this is not possible through a container registry and can be managed with tools such as Portainer¹⁹, for their deployment onto the Participants Infrastructure.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/soivity/edc-broker-server-extension>

¹⁸ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.portainer.io/>

Figure 4 - GEMINI Data Space Data Component Diagram and Integration with External Data Sources

Figure 4 depicts how data is integrated in the GEMINI Data Space, showcasing the MVDS with the addition of an App Store/Container Registry and Data Integration Apps. It emphasizes that a single IDS Connector is capable of accommodating various data sources, while multiple IDS Apps can be utilized to facilitate the integration of diverse data sources. Following an agile approach, Table 1 is set to outline the Data Adapter Apps intended for development on each iteration, with the final selection to be determined according to the requirements of the project’s partners.

Data Type	Data Direction	Implementation Details	Iteration cycle	Notes
API Server	Source/Sink	APIs	1 st	For Pull requests
API Client	Source/Sink	APIs	1 st	For Push Requests
Folders/Files	Source/Sink	SAMBA, NTFS	1 st	
Storage Object	Sink	Minio	2 nd	
Streams	Source/Sink	Apache Kafka	2 nd	Mqtt support for IoT devices upon request
SQL-Databases	Source/Sink	Postgres	2 nd	Support for additional DBs upon request

Table 1 - List of IDS Adapter Apps

One point of concern is Data Anonymization, particularly due to the focus of GEMINI project on Shared Mobility services. Initial evaluations of datasets from the Amsterdam MLL have revealed concerns regarding the inclusion of sensitive details, such as visited locations by users and their personal information. Ensuring the anonymity of data is paramount for the secure exchange of information within the GEMINI Data Space, presenting an opportunity for the development of data applications capable of anonymizing these datasets. These data applications could be deployed on the IDS Connector of the Data Owner/Provider, thereby preserving data sovereignty and data governance.

2.3.3 Roles and responsibilities

In accordance with the IDS Business Layer, specific roles and responsibilities must be considered in designing the GEMINI Data Space. Three basic roles under the broad category of Data Supplier are identified. Firstly, the Data Creator role refers to entities or individuals generating data, such as Mobility Users commuting within the MLLs within the GEMINI project. Typically, Data Owners, including Mobility Service Providers, Shared Mobility Providers, and City authorities and Services, collect and store this data. These entities usually have some form of written agreements with the Data Creators, allowing them to use the data in compliance with national privacy regulations like the GDPR. The Data Provider role is attributed to those making the data technically accessible within the GEMINI data space, acting as intermediaries for Data Discovery and Transfer without storing or directly accessing the data.

Conversely, two roles are defined on the Data Customer side. Data Consumers who are responsible for providing the necessary software components like the IDS Connectors. The actual Data Users are the GEMINI technical partners, who utilize the data to deliver value-added services for the project, such as the BI Platform in Task 4.2 or the fleet maintenance tool in Task 4.1. Data Users within the GEMINI Data Space might take on the roles of Data Creators and Data Owners if they generate data that can be shared within the data space, utilizing the same IDS Connector for such tasks—though currently, no specific use cases have been identified. Most other roles identified in the Business Layer, including Data Broker, App Developer, Owner or Provider, and Identity Creator and Provider, are assumed by the GEMINI Data Space Implementors, KONNECTA and INLECOM.

2.3.4 Processes

Onboarding Phase

Each Partner will need to assume and state the role of the Data Owner or User or both if applicable. For those in the Data Owner role, it's necessary to submit a list of data sources that they are willing to share within the GEMINI Data Space. This is required to finalize the list of Adapter Apps as presented on Table 1, and implement them accordingly.

Likewise, the partners assuming the Data User role are expected to specify how they intend to integrate the data into their digital platforms.

Regarding the required infrastructure, each project partner interested in participating the GEMINI Data Space, should be equipped with an IDS Connector, with two potential approaches to address this need. The first involves installing the IDS Connector within the participant's own IT infrastructure, enabling direct access to data sources/sinks while ensuring security through measures like reverse proxies or firewalls. Figure 5 demonstrates this design. The second option is the use of an IDS Connector deployed on external IT resources, on public cloud providers (e.g. AWS, Azure, GCP) or a private cloud of IDS Connector provider - Figure 6. This latter approach, essentially offering the IDS Connector as a Service, simplifies integration into IDS, especially for the non-technical participants. However, the integration with the data sources/sinks requires additional security measurements to safeguard against unauthorized access to the data.

Figure 5 - IDS Connector deployed on Local Infrastructure

Figure 6 - IDS Connector as a Service deployment.

KNT will offer support for both solutions but given that remote access to partners' infrastructure might be limited, or infrastructure resources might not be available, the second approach is advised.

Establishing the identity of each participant is fundamental to fostering trust. To accomplish this, every partner should be authenticated using a valid X.509 Certificate. These essential certificates can be procured in one of two ways: either through an Identity Manager alongside a corresponding Certification Authority (CA) managed by the GEMINI Data Space

Administrators, KNT and INLECOM, or by obtaining certificates from recognized public providers, like Let's Encrypt²⁰.

Data Offering

Each project participant that would like to offer data through the GEMINI Data Space, has two possible ways to accomplish it. The first, commonly adopted within the GEMINI project, would be the direct data offering and exchange between the Data Provider and the Data Consumer. In most MLLs the entities involved have a good knowledge of the available datasets and a general understanding of potential applications. In such scenarios, Data Owners shall directly provide metadata descriptions of their datasets via their IDS Connectors. However, in typical data space use cases, the Data Owner would not be aware of which partners would be interested in the provided data. In this case the data description should be advertised through the Metadata Broker.

In both cases, KNT will provide assistance in the creation of the Data Description to the involved partners. This description will include details on the dataset type, a contract outlining usage policies, and a set of tags to simplify dataset searchability.

A critical aspect to consider is the access policies, which the Data Owner must define. These policies are to be enforced by all IDS Connectors within the GEMINI Data Space, ensuring controlled and compliant data access and usage. Table 2 present the list of policies that are planned to be implemented.

Access Policy	Description	Parameters
Unrestricted	No limitation for data retrieval	
Maximum number of Times Accessed	It can be used for demo data access or as base for data rental	Number of data exchanges that are allowed
Maximum Data Size offered	It can be used for demo data access or as base for data rental	Size of Data that can be exchanged. In TB, GB
Time limited	Allow access to the data up to a specific number of days or a specific date.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of Days • Date

Table 2 - Access Policies description

Data Exchange

Based on the Offering process described above, Data Consumer would need to follow one of the two options to find the required dataset. The next step would be to accept the offered contract and finally to start the data downloading.

There are two main types of data assets that can be exchanged through the GEMINI Data Space. The first type is static datasets. These are data that needs to be exchanged in a one-off manner. They may refer to infrastructure maps, shared vehicles specifications, regulatory and zoning Information, parking and recharging stations positions, Public Transportation schedules and routes. In some cases, these static data might present some modifications over long periods of time, in which case a new data exchange might take place. The second type is related to real time data, such as shared mobility user statistics, traffic data, vehicle trip information, and reservation statistics. GEMINI Data Space will be able to support the exchange of both types.

²⁰ <https://letsencrypt.org/>

The following types of data exchange shall be supported by GEMINI Data Space

- Pull. The Data Consumer may request data from the Data Providers over the IDS Connectors Interfaces. Figure 7 - Data Exchange Pull
- Push. The Data Provider shall push newly available data to the Data Consumers that have been registered and agreed in the relative contract. Figure 8 - Data Exchange Push
- Scheduled. This flow shall apply to both data exchange forms defined previously. Schedulers shall be defined to allow the data exchange at predetermined intervals. Given that this functionality is not available in the IDS Connectors, a Data App shall be responsible for operating this process. Figure 9 - Data Exchange Scheduler
- Event Driven. Like the "Scheduled", this flow shall allow data exchange between two GEMINI Data Space participants to be triggers based on external events. This would be useful for Data sources based on watched directories - where the addition of new files or the modification of existing one - shall touch off a data exchange, or as a means to support IoT devices and constant stream of dataflows. Figure 10 - Data Exchange Event Driven

Figure 7 - Data Exchange Pull

Figure 8 - Data Exchange Push

Figure 9 - Data Exchange Scheduler

Figure 10 - Data Exchange Event Driven

A challenge that needs to be tackled is initiating the scheduled data exchanges.

One issue to be addressed is the triggering of scheduled data exchanges. The EDC does not support this process out of the box and therefore the introduction of an additional IDS Application is required. In line with the terminology of the IDS-RAM, a Control App²¹ will be essential. The application will have the following functional requirements:

- Schedule management: Provide an interface for configuring the data exchange frequency. This interface could be a configuration file, similar to cron²² scheduler on Linux OS, a Rest Interface or a Graphical User Interface. For the first iteration, the configuration file approach shall be selected.
- Reporting of the transfer Execution: This is crucial for failed cases and will allow the Data Exchange participants and the data space administrators to resolve these issues.

²¹ https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/ids-ram-4/layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3-layers-of-the-reference-architecture-model/3_5_0_system_layer/3_5_3_app_store_and_data_apps

²² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cron>

Figure 11 - Scheduled Data Exchange

2.3.5 Use Cases

The primary objective of the GEMINI Data Space is to maximize participant engagement and foster data-driven applications by enhancing data discoverability. At the time of writing this report, four use cases have been identified where project partners serve as Data Producers.

One partner from the Amsterdam Living Lab (LL), will provide operational data related to shared mobility services. The partner offers a white-label platform utilized by shared vehicle operators for managing users and vehicles, with available data primarily incorporating vehicle trip and reservation information.

Similarly, partners from Paris and Copenhagen Living Labs offer similar opportunities. For instance, the Paris-based partner's business model includes shared vehicle operations and managing Electric Vehicle (EV) charging stations, which allows them to provide data concerning the charging process.

An important consideration for the Copenhagen-based partner is the management of Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs) between exchange partners within the IDS GEMINI Data Space framework, ensuring that sensitive information remains protected.

An interesting use case is the one of partner Caruso, who is offering a dataplace through a dedicated portal. Caruso has developed a marketplace of data for connected vehicles, sourced from major vehicle manufacturers and can be accessed through APIs for interested parties. This setup allows for various pricing models and represents a compelling use case of how an IDS Data Space could interact with established data marketplaces. For partners like Caruso, this presents a valuable opportunity to enhance visibility and attract more potential customers, while data consumers benefit from support in implementing data-driven applications.

2.3.6 Data Space Infrastructure

All IDS Components shall be deployed as containers, as discussed in 2.3.2. To further enhance the GEMINI Data Space capabilities, different tools and platforms shall be used based on the deployment environment.

For central IDS components like the Identity Provider, IDS Broker, and Container Hub, deploying a centralized Kubernetes²³ cluster is recommended. This strategy facilitates the easier scaling of application instances, enhanced monitoring of component health, and the implementation of version-controlled updates through helm²⁴ charts.

Regarding the IDS Connector, the deployment method will vary based on the actual location of each connector. For connectors situated within a Partner's infrastructure, the use of Docker Containers shall be advised. Considering that IDS Apps will be sideloaded onto the IDS Connectors, the use of Docker compose²⁵ add-on is recommended. A single file will encompass all the required containers for deployment, thus minimizing the complexity and potential errors during the initial setup phase. The deployment requirements for such cases should be the following.

- Docker²⁶ CE or another compatible container engine. The host OS should be preferable Linux, but it will also be applicable for Windows Operating system with the use of a licensed version of Docker Desktop.
- At least 2 CPUs, 8 GBs or RAM and 50 GBs hard disk space in the form of SSD. In case of high data exchange load, more hardware resources might be required.
- Public Internet Address – Optional a Fully Qualified Domain name registered to public DNS infrastructure.
- 4 host ports should be accessible from the public Internet (the ports can be defined dynamically during installation and are required for the intercommunication of the IDS Components and the data exchange).

For the Containers offers as a Service, utilizing a Kubernetes cluster shall be the preferred approach, enabling the efficient reuse of available resources. To ensure the isolation of each participant's IDS Connector and IDS Apps, the use of Kubernetes namespace²⁷ shall be used. Additional methods such as Kubernetes network policies and storage isolation shall be considered. It is imperative to note that the IDS Connectors and the IDS App are not storing the actual datasets that are exchanged between two IDS Participants, but only Metadata, therefore the main concern is the encryption of data on the move, compare to solutions that should consider the encryption of data at rest. For the last measurement Data Owners and Data Users are responsible for its implementation.

Another important aspect is establishing secure connections between IDS as a Service and the Data Sources or Sinks. To ensure this requirement the use of secure protocols, such as HTTPS and SFTP, shall be used. Additionally, setting up VPN connections between the data sources and the IDS Connectors using the WireGuard²⁸ tool will be carried out, whenever this is applicable or requested in order to further enhance security. Figure 6 depicts this connection option.

2.3.7 Data Space Implementation Plan

The development of an IDSA Data Space involves developing various software components, deploying, and configuring them across multiple use cases and physical locations. Consequently,

²³ <https://kubernetes.io/>

²⁴ <https://helm.sh/>

²⁵ <https://docs.docker.com/compose/>

²⁶ <https://www.docker.com/>

²⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/security/multi-tenancy/#namespaces>

²⁸ <https://www.wireguard.com/>

the implementation of the GEMINI Data Space will adopt a multistage approach to meet the project's specific requirements. These stages include:

Define Business and Functional requirements.

During this initial stage, we are collecting business and functional requirements from project partners. Critical factors influencing the data space architecture include the types of data sources or sinks and any necessary data transformations. Given that participant numbers and needs may evolve throughout the project, this task will be ongoing for much of its duration.

On Figure 12 there are two distinct phases, the first one gathers the information for the MVDS and the pilot solution, while the second one will be built on-top of the first phase on M18 and it is designed to attract more partners into the GEMINI Data Space.

Architecture Design

In this phase, we have selected essential IDS components and outline the basic integration concepts as detailed in 2.3.2. This phase is considered as finalized. Possible minor modifications to the architecture shall be handled as part of the implementation phases and will be reported in the final review on M36-MS4.

Develop MVDS

This stage states the first iteration of the GEMINI Data Space, based on the MVDS with additional features to accommodate the initial use cases outlined in this section. This phase will also see the development and deployment of the most needed data adapter applications, and control apps for use by the partners mentioned in section 2.3.5.

A first demonstration of the MVDS to the Project participants would take place on M16 during the "Local MLLs Physical Workshops" as stated in Table 10 in the grant agreement document. During the workshop we are expecting to verify the pilot use cases and start discussion.

After the workshops the deployment of the first MVDS along with the onboarding of the partners of the pilot Use case shall conclude the first phase of the GEMINI Data Space on M18. After this date the data space should be available to all partners.

Implementation of additional data apps and IDS Components.

This phase has been allocated for covering the needs of new data space participants or new Use case. Requirements for this phase shall flow in through the pilot users, the workshops outcome and the second phase of interviews with interested partners, as stated on the next phase.

Onboarding more UC and Project Partners.

This is the second phase of the GEMINI data space implementation. A similar circle of gathering requirements, developing new applications, and finally onboarding the partners shall conclude the specific task.

Figure 12 presents this implementation plan in a Gantt chart form.

Figure 12 - Data Space Implementation Plan

3 GEMINI BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE PLATFORM

The primary goal of a Business Intelligence (BI) platform is to transform raw data and information into actionable insights. This involves a systematic process, beginning with the collection and harmonisation of data, followed by analysis and visualisation. Ultimately, the aim is to empower users to make well-informed decisions based on the insights gained.

In terms of the data analysis needs this process in GEMINI will take place in three phases and their respective sub-step as each of them are summarised in Figure 13. More specific, during the first month of the project lifetime, the focus has been on understanding the objectives and goals of GEMINI MLLs partners and operators. This understanding is crucial for identifying key research areas and acquiring relevant data, whether sourced internally or from external sources if needed. Subsequently, the exploration of identified key activities and results sources is detailed in the following section.

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Figure 13 Lifecycle of a Data Analysis³¹

The GEMINI Business Intelligence platform will be tailored to cater to the diverse requirements of project stakeholders, including city officials, urban planners, and mobility services operators. It will provide a comprehensive solution spanning from fleet management to monitoring service quality metrics and city-level statistics. Additionally, the GEMINI BI platform aims to streamline the integration of data from various sources into a unified, coherent view, as well as help users to discover and/or establish relationships between data features. Moreover, it aims to facilitate policy-making decisions based on advanced BI and data modelling capabilities.

Furthermore, within the GEMINI BI platform, users will access a range of visualization tools customised to their analytical requirements. These options include dynamic maps for spatial data representation, aiding stakeholders in visualising geographical trends. Graphs will depict relationships, trends, and comparisons within datasets, facilitating efficient identification of correlations and outliers. The platform will also offer diverse chart types like bar charts, pie charts, and line charts, providing intuitive visual representations of data distribution, composition, and temporal trends.

In the subsequent sections, we will delve into the specific capabilities of the GEMINI BI platform, including available models and key analytics. These insights stem from interviews conducted with project stakeholders and relevant partners, with a particular focus on shared mobility initiatives.

²⁹ <https://graduate.northeastern.edu/resources/data-analysis-project-lifecycle/>

³⁰ <https://intellipaas.com/blog/tutorial/data-analytics-tutorial/data-analytics-lifecycle/>

³¹ A. Ball, Review of data management lifecycle models, 2012 ,

3.1 GEMINI Platform BI Analytics

Focusing on enhancing operational efficiency and productivity within shared mobility schemes, the GEMINI BI platform aims to offer robust intelligence capabilities tailored to address key challenges. The goal is that through the GEMINI Business Intelligence (BI) platform, project stakeholders can enhance their business operations, city-level reporting processes, and new mobility services. This is achieved by seamlessly connecting to various data sources such as vehicles (e.g., car OEMs), mobility operators' systems, and city infrastructure/open data sets, utilizing advanced analytical techniques including algorithms and statistical methods. For this reason, the platform aims to provide robust intelligence capabilities for large-scale data analysis, business intelligence, and enterprise analytics, including interactive features like live filtering, sorting, and grouping that enable stakeholders to engage in real-time exploration of datasets.

Finally, based on the preliminary analysis of project UCs and structured interviews conducted with MLLs stakeholders and shared mobility operators, the key business intelligence needs and metrics to support day-to-day management and operations of shared mobility services were identified and are presented below.

3.1.1 Vehicles Management and Demand Management Analytics

Effective vehicle utilization is a key element in fleet management, influencing operational costs and productivity within shared mobility schemes, as emphasized by project mobility operators. To address this challenge, the GEMINI BI platform endeavours to provide comprehensive insights and analytics on fleet performance and assets underutilization. Leveraging information and data from the whole lifecycle of the mobility service, the platform will generate detailed reports encompassing a spectrum of data, including trip characteristics, booking specifics, and fuel consumption trends. Additionally, particular focus will be given to analytics related to electric vehicles (e.g., cars, mopeds, scooters, etc.), including efficient charging, battery scheduling, and repositioning strategies. This holistic approach ensures that fleet managers have the necessary tools to optimize vehicle utilization and enhance the overall efficiency of their operations.

Table 3 - Identified Data and Sources for Vehicle Monitoring and Management

Analytics Category	Key Metrics or Analytics	Source
Vehicle Utilization		
	Vehicle occupancy rate and downtime	Mobility service systems/database
	Classification of underutilized assets	Mobility service systems/database
	Trip characteristics analysis	Mobility service systems/database
	Total Booking and booking per vehicle data analysis	Booking app / Mobility service system/database
	Fuel consumption patterns	Vehicle itself or charging station

	Fuel efficiency strategies	Vehicle itself/ Mobility service system/database
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Moreover, the infusion of AI models into fleet management aims to boost productivity by optimizing deployment strategies, predicting demand patterns, and suggesting efficient planning and scheduling. Through the utilization of telemetric data sourced from the cars and the analysis of time series and booking data, AI algorithms offer invaluable insights that streamline operations. For instance, machine learning algorithms facilitate demand forecasting, which plays a pivotal role in enhancing fleet management and resource allocation. By predicting usage patterns at specific times and locations, businesses can adjust their fleet distribution to align with anticipated demand fluctuations, ensuring sufficient vehicle availability and minimizing waiting times for customers.

Table 4 - GEMINI AI-Models focus areas

AI Driven	Strategy/Optimization
Deployment Strategies	Optimizes the allocation of vehicles across different locations or routes to maximize their usage and minimize idle time, ensuring efficient deployment according to demand fluctuations.
Demand Pattern Prediction	Predicts future demand patterns based on historical data, enabling proactive adjustments in fleet size and distribution to meet anticipated demand, thus optimizing resource allocation and reducing the risk of under- or over-supply.
Efficient Charging Schedules for Electric Vehicles	Recommends optimal charging schedules for electric vehicles based on factors such as battery capacity, charging station availability, and electricity pricing, to minimize charging time, reduce energy costs, and ensure fleet readiness, enhancing the efficiency of electric vehicle operations.

In addition, another key focuses and according to the interest of MLLs partners are the analysis of driver behaviour, this emerges as another critical area in boosting vehicle utilization and curbing operational costs. By gathering and analysing data from vehicle onboard diagnostics units' businesses gain insights into driving patterns, enabling them to implement real-time feedback mechanisms that incentivize safer driving practices.

Finally, another key area of GEMINI platform BI analytics will be the preventive maintenance aiming to ensure fleet vehicles operate at peak efficiency while mitigating the risk of costly breakdowns. Through automated reports from GEMINI BI on engine performance statistics, businesses can proactively schedule maintenance tasks and address potential issues before they escalate, thus avoiding the need for emergency repairs and towing services, leading to substantial cost savings over time.

Table 5 - Identified Data and Sources for around Vehicle Maintenance

Analytics Category	Key Metrics or Analytics	Source
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Preventive Maintenance	Automated maintenance reports	Booking app / Mobility service system/database
	Proactive maintenance scheduling	Mobility service system/database
	Cost savings from emergency repairs mitigation Reduction in towing services cost	Mobility service system/database

3.1.2 Cost and Pricing Strategy Analytics

Another key aspect in shared mobility fleet management, close related also with fleet management and utilization, is the pricing strategy followed. Dynamic pricing strategies based historic and expected usage patterns help optimize resources and increase operational and revenues efficiencies.

Price discrimination and/or dynamic pricing scheme can play an important role in maximizing revenue and user satisfaction while also considering vehicle operating costs, as well as maintaining competitiveness and profitability. In addition, dynamic pricing schemes foster resilience and adaptability to different user/travellers' behaviour and changing market conditions,

For example, GEMINI BI platform will provide suggestions and pricing schemes incentivizing customers to rent vehicles during off-peak hours, balancing demand across different times of the day and optimizing fleet utilization. Moreover, pricing decisions must remain responsive to shifting market dynamics and unexpected events. Utilizing what-if scenarios, such as analysing demand fluctuations due to unforeseen events or competitor presence, allows businesses to anticipate potential impacts on pricing strategies. This foresight enables proactive adjustments to price models, ensuring continued alignment with market demand and maximizing revenue opportunities.

Finally, preparing for service downtime is paramount in maintaining operational continuity. Understanding how unforeseen maintenance needs might affect resource allocation and pricing adjustments enables businesses to mitigate potential disruptions effectively. By factoring in scenarios such as parking capacity limitations due to local construction or events, fleet managers can ensure seamless operations and minimize customer inconvenience.

Table 6 - BI Platform and Analytics Offerings

Analytics Category	Key Metrics or Analytics
Peak/off-peak hours analysis	Identify peak and off-peak hours to optimize pricing strategies and incentivize rentals during low-demand periods.
Price elasticity	Analyse how changes in pricing affect demand elasticity to optimize revenue.
Pricing trends	Monitor trends in pricing adjustments over time to identify effective pricing strategies.

Revenue optimization	Track revenue generated from dynamic pricing strategies to evaluate effectiveness.
Financial Metrics	
Revenue growth	Track revenue growth over time to evaluate the overall effectiveness of pricing strategies.
profitability analysis	Analyse profitability metrics to ensure pricing strategies align with profitability goals while maximizing revenue and customer satisfaction.
Competitive Analysis Metrics	
Competitor pricing analysis	Monitor pricing strategies of competitors to remain competitive and adjust pricing accordingly.
Market share analysis	Track changes in market share in response to pricing strategies and market dynamics.

3.1.3 Environmental and Sustainability Analytics

Environmental and sustainability analytics are essential components of both modern fleet management and for city level officials aiming to improve cities and citizens footprint in line with EC targets of net-zero.

In this context also shared mobility can help both to minimize their environmental footprint, reduce resource consumption, and promote sustainable practices throughout their operations. By leveraging data-driven insights and implementing targeted strategies both public and private sector can achieve their environmental goals while maintaining operational efficiency and profitability. To accommodate both user groups—public sector officials and mobility operators—on the Business Intelligence platform, the interface should offer tailored features and analytics dashboards. Here's a breakdown of how the platform can serve each user group:

By providing specialized dashboards and analytics tools for both public sector officials and mobility operators, the Business Intelligence platform can facilitate data-driven decision-making, promote sustainability, and improve the efficiency of transportation systems in the city. This table provides a clear overview of the tailored dashboards and features designed for each user group on the Business Intelligence platform.

Table 7 - BI Platform User Types and Features

User Group	Dashboard / Features
Public Sector Officials	
	Modal Split Monitoring Dashboard
	Visual representations of modal split trends over time
	Comparative analysis of modal split between different areas
	Aggregate Statistics
	Comprehensive statistics on transportation-related metrics

	Emissions data, including CO2 emissions and trends
	Data on traffic
Mobility Operators	Environmental Impact Dashboard
	Analysis of fleet emissions, fuel consumption, and air quality
	Driver Carbon Footprint Dashboard
	Comparative analysis of emissions across different vehicle types

3.1.4 GEMINI BI Data Modelling and Optimization Strategy

Based on the key areas and the analytics of the GEMINI BI platform described previously, this section explores the application of various optimization, statistical, and ML/AI techniques within this context. The preliminary analysis relies on relevant research and datasets provided by MLLs mobility operators, including e-scooter, e-bike, and shared (EV) car services. The goal is to lay the groundwork for selecting and applying the most relevant techniques in the next period, leveraging these datasets to provide new insights and advanced capabilities to end users. The key research areas under investigation are summarized as follows:

1. **Driving Behaviour Analysis:** To analyse driving behaviour using Machine Learning (ML), several existing models and techniques can be employed. Supervised learning, where the ML algorithm is trained on labelled datasets, is one common approach. For example, Support Vector Machines (SVMs) or Random Forest classifiers can classify driving events such as aggressive acceleration, harsh braking, or speeding based on predefined labels. Cars equipped with accelerometers monitor this information, and such datasets may be available from project partners based on historical trips. Unsupervised learning techniques can also identify patterns and anomalies in driving data without labelled datasets. Clustering algorithms like K-means can group similar driving patterns, helping identify common behaviours among drivers or detect outliers that deviate from typical driving norms.
2. **Preventive Maintenance:** Based on the GEMINI BI platform's available datasets, preventive maintenance analysis can be incorporated using statistical or ML methods. Simple time series analysis, including forecasting techniques, can analyse historical engine performance data to identify trends. Historical time series of engine performance can predict future performance, aiding proactive maintenance scheduling. More advanced techniques, such as survival analysis or recurrent neural networks (RNNs), can improve forecast accuracy. For example, survival analysis techniques like the Cox proportional hazards model can predict the likelihood of engine failure over time, considering various covariates and failure risk factors. RNNs can analyse sequential engine sensor data to predict the time to failure or the remaining useful life of critical components, enabling timely maintenance interventions to prevent unexpected breakdowns and optimize fleet performance.
3. **Demand and Pricing Forecasting:** The goal is to predict or anticipate different usage patterns for specific times and locations, enhancing fleet management and resource allocation for MLLs operators. Time series forecasting models like seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average (SARIMA), Vector Autoregressive Model (VAR), Error Correction Model (ECM),

or ETS³² can predict demand using historical usage patterns and bookings. By integrating demand forecasting, an operator can ensure sufficient vehicle availability, reducing customer waiting times. These models can be smoothed using filters and seasonal detrending techniques to improve forecast performance. Additionally, investigating the correlation and impact of exogenous factors helps identify relationships between demand and factors such as time, weather, or promotions could another area of investigation.

4. Battery Health Monitoring for EVs: Implementing ML models to monitor and predict the health of electric vehicle (EV) batteries involves developing algorithms that analyse battery performance data to detect potential issues and forecast battery degradation. Suitable ML techniques for this task include Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, Support Vector Regression (SVR), and Gaussian Process Regression (GPR). These models predict future battery health based on past charging cycles, environmental conditions, and usage patterns. They can provide point estimates and confidence intervals, enabling informed decision-making regarding charging strategies to ensure battery reliability.

To enhance the operational efficiency and decision-making capabilities of the GEMINI BI platform and its users, optimization techniques and their potential application will also be investigated. These techniques, could be also combined/leverage some of the outcomes from the statistical analysis, aiming to increase the sustainability of project new mobility services. In addition, different appropriate techniques for modelling such problems that will be evaluated to use include:

1. Linear Programming (LP) maximises revenue or minimises costs by optimizing pricing and resource allocation, considering constraints like vehicle availability, operating costs, and revenue targets.
2. Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) is beneficial for integer-restricted decision variables, such as determining optimal vehicle allocations to stations or pricing tiers.
3. Genetic Algorithms (GA) handle complex, nonlinear problems efficiently, evolving potential solutions over generations to find optimal pricing and resource allocations. Simulated Annealing explores solution spaces for near-optimal solutions in complex, nonlinear optimisation problems, useful for pricing and resource allocation amidst demand fluctuations and operational constraints.
4. SBM (Data Envelopment Analysis) and DEA (Stochastic Frontier Analysis) techniques can be used to leverage historical data to discern the most efficient performers. In case of GEMINI this could include factors such as vehicle usage, encompassing the number of trips completed and the total distance travelled, alongside revenue generated, which encapsulates the total income derived from rentals per vehicle, and other operating costs. Furthermore, this analysis could be further enriched with Sensitivity analysis. Sensitivity analysis assesses how optimal solutions may change under varying parameters such as demand fluctuations, service downtimes, and parking capacity limitations. Such analysis could help MLLs operators to design or evaluate different strategies to maintain profitability under various circumstances. More detailed techniques for sensitivity analysis that will be investigated include:
 - I. Scenario Analysis: Evaluates the impact of different scenarios on key performance indicators by varying input parameters.
 - II. Monte Carlo Simulation: Generates multiple random scenarios to simulate uncertain conditions and analyse their effects.

³² <https://www.statsmodels.org/v0.12.2/examples/notebooks/generated/ets.html>

- III. Tornado Diagrams: Visualizes the sensitivity of output variables to changes in input parameters.
- IV. Sensitivity Tables: Systematically varies input parameters to observe their impact on output variables.
- V. Break-Even Analysis: Identifies the threshold where changes in input parameters affect profitability or performance metrics.

Concluding, this section introduced preliminary results based on user needs, partners' available data, and various statistical and machine learning (ML) techniques for producing data-driven insights aligned with strategic interests and project partners. These initial steps aim to serve as a foundation for the core analysis that will take place in the upcoming months, experimenting with and testing various ML and statistical techniques relevant to each area to identify the most effective models for analysis. Final decisions on specific techniques or models will be reported in the next version of the report, based on the final datasets and user feedback about the modelling work results.

3.2 BI's Functional and non-functional Requirements

The following functional requirements have been identified to apply for the GEMINI BI Platform.

Table 8 - BI Functional Requirements

ID	Requirement	Description
FR1	Data Ingestion	The platform should be able to ingest data from various data sources or through the GEMINI Data Space.
FR2	Data Storage	Data should be stored in platform's data warehouse
FR3	Model Library	The Platform should offer a library of reusable models that can be used for prediction or simulation use cases.
FR4	Model Execution	The platform should be able to orchestrate the execution of integrated models, by ingesting the required input and storing the generated output in Platform's data warehouse.
FR5	Business Analytic Services	On-Demand business analytic services should be callable through Platform's Portal.
FR6	Dashboard and Visualisation Services	The Platform should provide understandable dashboards to present the output of the hosted models and analytic services by using plots, maps, tables and graphs.

Similarly, Table 9 list the non-functional requirements:

Table 9 - BI Platform - Non-Functional Requirements

ID	Requirement	Description
NF1	Identity and Access Management	Platform should support the concept of the „The principle of least privilege“
NF2	GDPR Compliance	All data should be stored or used in compliance with GDPR rules

ID	Requirement	Description
NF3	Multi-tenancy Support	The platform should support separated solutions for each MLL. Access should be allowed in accordance with NF1
NF4	Data Storage security	Data at rest should be encrypted. Databases should use credentials - Host's should use encrypted drives
NF5	Data in transit should be secured	Data in motion, either between services or through the Platform's portal should be encrypted through the use of proper security protocols
NF6	Performance	Support the parallel execution of at least 3 models.
NF7	Scalability	The Platform should be able to scale out across more machines to handle increased load (model execution distribution)
NF8	Documentation	Detailed documentation regarding platforms operations should be available.
NF9	Interoperability	Provide easy integration with partner's platform either directly or through the GEMINI Data Space
NF10	Disaster Recovery	Provide a mechanism for backing up the Operation and Configuration data. Provide a restoration mechanism.

3.3 GEMINI Platform BI Architecture

The GEMINI Business Analytics platform shall be revised version of the Digital Twin platform developed in the LEAD³³ Project. More details regarding LEAD's Digital Twin Digital Twin platform architecture deliverable [4]. The Digital Twin platform core functionality was the execution of prediction and simulation models and the user creation of simulation scenarios that were a chain of models. The BI platform shall build on-top of existing framework, shifting the focus on Business Analytics by offering insights into raw data provided by the MLLs of the GEMINI project. At the same time, the platform will retain its capabilities to orchestrate models through its advance Simulation Environment.

3.3.1 Conceptual Architecture

Based on the C4 modelling lean graphical notation technique for architecture of the BI Platform, Figure 14 presents the system context architecture of the solution. In this diagram, we present the BI platform at the centre of the diagram, surrounded by its main users and the other systems that interacts with.

³³ <https://www.leadproject.eu/>

System Context Diagram GEMINI

Figure 14 - System Context Diagram

The Decision-Making Consultant is the primary user of the platform. Within the scope of GEMINI project this role can be assigned to a variety of professionals, including City Planners, Executive Managers, Marketing and Sales professionals of shared vehicles companies, as well as Environmental Analysts. In most cases, these actors are also users of the MLLs Systems. Each of these users interacts with the BI platform according to their specific needs and responsibilities, requiring tailored access levels, interfaces, and functionalities.

Beyond providing macroscopic analysis and reports, the BI Platform serves as a digital twin of the physical world, delivering insights from near real-time data to Operations Managers at shared vehicle companies and customer support engineers.

The BI Platform shall be fed with data over the GEMINI Data Space. According to IDSA, the BI Platform shall assume the role of Data User. The data space facilitates data exchange via a unified channel, enhancing the solution's capability for interoperability.

3.3.2 Component Diagram

Drawing from the current architecture of the LEAD Digital Twin Platform and the specific needs of a BI Platform for Urban Mobility, Figure 15 illustrates the updated architecture of the BI Tool.

Container Diagram of BI Platform - GEMINI

Figure 15 - BI Platform Container Diagram

Starting from the bottom of the Figure 15, we will provide a short description of each component and emphasize in the newly created or modified ones according to the BI tool requirements.

Data Connectors and IDS Adapter

The two components are tasked with data acquisition via the GEMINI Data Space. Specific Data Connectors shall be developed to seamlessly communicate with the newly designed IDS Adapter App for the BI Platform. The primary objective for both applications is to supply data to the BI Platform in an agnostic way.

The Data shall be forwarded to the Event Streaming System (e.g. Apache Kafka³⁴), which will be responsible for the data distribution within the platform.

Data Storage

The incoming data will be housed in the Data Storage layer. Given the data's characteristics – time series information from shared vehicles trips – the use of time-series database, like InfluxDB³⁵ or TimeScaleDB³⁶, is being considered as the primary repository. The use of existing or new services for data transformation shall be considered according to the final business requirements. An addition of the transformation services shall be the creation of a Metadata Catalogue (e.g. Datahub³⁷ or Neo4j³⁸) for all the data stored in the Platform. This aims to deepen the insight derived from the MLLs, thereby enabling data-driven applications.

Data Analytics

A series of microservices shall be developed to fulfil the analytics requirements presented in “3.1 GEMINI Platform BI Analytics” section. Each Service shall offer an API to allow its integration with the Visualization Services. The services may consume data either from the Storage Layer or the Event Streaming System

Model Library and Orchestration

The Platform features a collection of models that can be used to construct specific use case scenarios. These models are executed by the Model Orchestrator module, which is built on Apache Airflow³⁹. The LEAD project has outlined a detailed process for integrating new models as well as for creating model chains. The orchestration module plays a crucial role in running simulations and generating business reports at specific intervals.

Visualization Services

The platform shall provide a range of intuitive dashboards designed to align with the Platform's focus on Business Analysis. The following categories of dashboards shall be explored:

- Operation Performance
- Financial Overview
- Usage Trends
- Environmental Impact
- Demand Forecasting

Additionally, to accommodate the needs of various partners, each dashboard and its underlying services will be built to support multi-tenancy. This ensures data isolation and customized business analysis for each partner using the platform.

Authentication and Routing Gateway

This layer will serve as the primary entry point to backend services, providing a centralized point for enforcing authentication and authorization for end-users. This setup enhances system security by implementing a fine-grained access control. Furthermore, it will provide better scalability through functionalities like the decoupling of services and load-balancing of incoming traffic across multiple service instances.

³⁴ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

³⁵ <https://www.influxdata.com/>

³⁶ <https://www.timescale.com/>

³⁷ <https://datahubproject.io/>

³⁸ <https://neo4j.com/>

³⁹ <https://airflow.apache.org/>

3.3.3 Technical Architecture

In this section a description of the newly added features and components that will allow the transformation of the Digital Twin platform into the BI platform for the GEMINI Project.

API Gateway

Towards a more mature platform, an API gateway is planning to be deployed fetching the benefits described in Authentication and Routing Gateway subsection.

The primary goals are.

- Provide a centralized security execution point. By that backend services are offloading the task of user authentication and authorization and focusing on the implementation of the business logic
- Provide an additional layer of security by not directly exposing backend services but hiding them behind a reverse proxy.

At the time this report is being written, two API Gateway's open-source projects are considered for integration, the Apache Apisix⁴⁰ and the Tyk API Gateway⁴¹, with the first one being the initial choice as an Apache top-level-project, which ensure the openness of the software.

Identity Provider

Both API gateways can fully interact with an Identity Providers, like Keycloak⁴², to offer multiple authentication methods, such as basic authentication, OAuth⁴³, OpenID⁴⁴ or Single Sign On⁴⁵ if the Keycloak acts as SSO Broker for an external Identity provider.

The Figure 16 demonstrates the basic authentication mechanism and how this is performed by the API gateway in conjunction with the Identity Provider module.

⁴⁰ <https://apisix.apache.org/>

⁴¹ <https://tyk.io/>

⁴² <https://www.keycloak.org/>

⁴³ <https://oauth.net/2/>

⁴⁴ <https://openid.net/>

⁴⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Single_sign-on

Figure 16 - Authentication with API Gateway and Identity Provider

As part of the Identity Provider integration the following roles shall be defined, and their access restrictions or permissions shall be enforced by the platform.

- **System Administrator:** These are users with global access to the system. They are responsible for creating Organizations, perform CRUD operations for other Users and maintain the platform.
- **System Power Users:** These are users that would be able to create, modify or delete organizations and they will have full access to these orgs, but they will not have access to other organizations.
- **System Viewers:** Specific group that would allow the members of it to view reports and dashboards from all the organizations or MLLs.
- **Organization Administrator:** The users of these group would have full access to all data and dashboards of the specific organization. Additionally, they would be able to create Organization users. To be noted that an organization would be either a Project Partner or an entire MLL - These would depend on the level of isolation that is required on the provided datasets.
- **Organization Users:** This group will be able to perform the most operations on their own organization, such as data uploading, data manipulation, creation, or modification of dashboards.
- **Organization Viewer:** Basic account that allows the members of it to view existing Dashboards of the Organization.

The following table is a map of the Business Roles to the BI Platform roles.

Table 10 - BI Platform Business Roles

Business Role	BI Role	Notes
Decision Makers, Policy Makers,	Organization Users, Org. Viewers	Usually, they will persons that would like to execute BI platform operation and view the results or the reports.
Organization Operators and Org. IT	Organization Admins	They will be responsible for data uploading and creation of the proper dashboards for the Organization decision makers.
Platform Development Team	System Power Users	System Power Users may allow other System Power Users to be added to their organization – This would allow development team
System Administrator	BI Platform Operators	Small teams of platform operators, that will be responsible for the proper
Project Reviewers	System Viewers	Persons with view access to the entire BI Platform – all MLLs. Some constrains shall be applied for datasets that require NDAs.

3.3.4 Model Catalogue

Given that the BI Platform is built on the LEAD Digital Twin Platform, it benefits from the models that are already integrated into it. However, not all of these models are suitable for reuse in the GEMINI Project due to their primary application in the last-mile logistics domain. Therefore, we have considered the following models for adaptation and potential integration into our current project needs:

EVC02

The EVC02 model aims to estimate the greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from electric vehicles associated with the electrical mix used to produce electricity. The method estimates the electric vehicles' CO₂eq emissions based on the sum of the mean electricity consumed by each vehicle (kWh) and the carbon intensity -the CO₂eq emissions per energy unit- of the electricity generation system of each region or study area (gCO₂eq/kWh).

COPERT

COPERT, the EU-standard vehicle emissions calculator, is a tool utilized for estimating emissions and energy consumption based on various factors such as vehicle population, mileage, speed, and ambient temperature. It is commonly employed for specific countries or regions. COPERT operates on a Windows server environment, where the model image interacts with input data in Microsoft Excel format. Requests are sent to the server, and the results, in either JSON⁴⁶ or XLSX

⁴⁶ <https://www.json.org/json-en.html>

format, are stored in a volume mount. For further details on COPERT, please refer to its official website⁴⁷ and the LEAD project website.

In addition to the models developed in previous EU projects, the GEMINI initiative will see the development of several new models specifically tailored to meet the project's current requirements. The initiation of these models has been driven by the specific needs identified within the project. It is important to note that this process is ongoing, and the model development is not yet finalized as new business requirements continue to emerge.

Emission Reduction Estimation Tool

This model, currently being developed by project partners CENEX, is designed to calculate the total emissions produced by a city's transportation services and the potential reductions achievable through the adoption of shared mobility services. The model will be delivered as part of the D2.1 GEMINI MLL Evaluation Framework, as a standalone tool. The BI Platform will then incorporate it, offering it as a Service, and will enhance it with additional features such as Role-Based Access Control, integration with external data sources, and permanent storage capabilities. Moreover, the platform will facilitate its integration into simulation scenarios, by enabling the chaining of multiple models to extend its utility and application.

3.3.5 User Interface and Dashboard Services

Dashboards serve as essential tools within any Business Intelligence (BI) Platform, providing a dynamic interface that visualizes data from diverse sources. These dashboards are designed not only to present complex information in an accessible format but also to enable users to derive actionable insights.

The dashboards on GEMINI BI Platform are specifically tailored to meet the unique needs of GEMINI project, offering Virtual Analytics Services, GIS map frames and the output of simulation and prediction models. They provide a comprehensive overview of key performance indicators (KPIs), such as traffic patterns, fleet vehicle performance, and usage trends, helping stakeholders make data-backed decisions that can lead to improved efficiency and reduced operational costs. These dashboards are interconnected with hyperlinks, enabling a seamless transition from high-level overviews to more detailed analytics concerning specific resources. For instance, Figure 17 displays the Paris MLL with the EV Hubs Layer activated. Selecting an individual EV Hub leads to a secondary page that provides comprehensive details about that specific hub (Figure 18).

⁴⁷ <https://copert.emisia.com/>

EV hubs can be found on the map with the colored Pins. The color of the pin presents the occupancy level of the hub at the given time - e.g It can be setup by the Parameters area

Figure 17 - MLL High-Level Dashboard

Figure 18 - EV Hub analytics Dashboard

The BI Platform will be provided as a Service to optimize hardware resources and maximize the reusability of software components. It will support multi-tenancy by creating virtual isolated spaces for each partner, ensuring data privacy and operational independence. Role-Based Access Control will be implemented to enforce distinct permission schemas for each tenant. Each user will have access to the Visual Analytics services and datasets that are relevant to their particular use case, ensuring a personalized and efficient user experience. The user creation and on-boarding process shall be managed by the KNT team, which will be responsible for assigning the correct roles and responsibilities for each user.

Finally, the main portal of the BI Platform shall be designed in accordance with the GEMINI trademark and colour scheme.

3.3.6 Implementation Plan

The implementation of the BI Platform will be based on the existing Digital Twin platform developed under EU Project Lead. This will allow for faster development of core services and enable us to focus available resources on implementing project-specific business cases.

Requirements gathering

During this stage, we are conducting interviews with MLLs actors to identify any business needs and opportunities for the BI Platform. Additionally, we are performing data assessments to understand the quality and availability of the data. This phase should be finalized after the conduction of the co-created workshops during M16.

Architecture Desing and Model Analysis

In this stage, we will define the BI Platform's architecture and provide the technical foundation for the models to be implemented. The basic architecture is already available as described in this report document. Additional features or capabilities are expected to be arise as part of the co-creation workshops. Nevertheless, given that the core functionalities are already knows, this allows us to enter to the implementation phase.

Development phase

The development phase is split into three major subtasks. The creation of the core backend services which are related with the data ingestion pipeline, and basic analytics services.

The second subtask is the creation of the front-end services that shall offer the interaction point with the end users.

The last subtask is the training and development of the AI/ML Models for the BI Platform.

As part of the process, we are allocating the last months of the Development phase for the testing of the entire platform. Finally, The BI platform shall be deployed on INLECOM's infrastructure and should be available for the Project partners by M20.

Integration with Gemini Data Space

During this phase the integration of the BI Platform with the GEMINI Data Space shall take place to allow for data ingestion pipelines to be fully functional. This would be the last step before the official release of the BI Platform, planned for M20.

Monitoring and Support

In this final stage, the BI Platform will be monitored for any abnormal or erroneous behaviour and provide fixes on user bugs. Depending on the end user feedback, additional feature might be considered for further implementation given the available time and there added value the new enhancements are providing.

Figure 19 presents a Gantt diagram of the implementation plan along with dates and milestones.

Figure 19 - BI Platform Implementation Plan

4 CONCLUSION

The GEMINI project aims to establish a sophisticated architecture around a data space and a Business Intelligence (BI) Platform, designed to enhance the shared mobility and MLLs NMS efficiency and sustainability. The first report, out of two addressing T4.2., aim to outline the research work on data space initiatives, as well as the technical architecture and components of GEMINI software solutions. Additionally, it highlights the development timeline and deployment of the GEMINI Data Space and BI Platform, emphasizing their role in fostering secure, interoperable data sharing across multiple stakeholders within the GEMINI Consortium.

In more detail, GEMINI Data Space, adhering to international data space standards, empowers stakeholders through decentralized data sharing mechanisms and robust security protocols. Its architecture ensures data sovereignty and seamless data exchange, supporting various use cases in the shared mobility industry. The inclusion of the International Data Space

Association framework ensures alignment with global standards. Starting from a Minimum Viable Data Space, the project demonstrates the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed data-sharing framework. As the GEMINI Data Space evolves, we are planning a series of targeted interactions to deepen engagement with project partners. Beginning with the co-creation workshops scheduled for Month 16, partners will have the opportunity to explore the main features of the GEMINI Data Space and discuss integration possibilities. Additionally, partners will be encouraged to become active members of the data space in the upcoming months.

In parallel, the goal of the GEMINI BI Platform is to leverage the data sets generated from MLL operations and transform them into actionable insights. Built on the successful Digital Twin Platform developed during the LEAD Project, the BI solution can integrate state-of-the-art ML/AI, analytics, and prediction models to support decision-making processes for city officials, urban planners, and shared mobility service operators. Additionally, a preliminary analysis of different optimization and AI/ML techniques is introduced, focusing on their application in the shared mobility domain and the needs identified through discussions with project partners and their data sources/systems. Furthermore, the BI platform will leverage data collected from diverse sources by integrating with the GEMINI Data Space, providing stakeholders with the tools needed to enhance operational efficiencies of shared fleet management processes, assess environmental impact, and improve shared mobility services planning through market trends and demand analysis. It also features highly intuitive, layered dashboards designed to facilitate easy onboarding for new users. These dashboards enhance user experience by filtering out unnecessary information and focusing on specific topics relevant to each use case.

The next phase for the GEMINI BI Platform involves engaging directly with project partners. At the co-creation workshop scheduled for M16, we will introduce the basic functionalities of the BI Platform, showcasing mock-up dashboards or a demo of the platform in develop. This session aims to collect feedback and identify additional requirements to refine the platform's development. Building on this feedback, the release of the BI Platform is scheduled for M20, where interested parties may start using it.

In conclusion, this report provided a solid foundation for guiding the development of the GEMINI software solutions. The next version will focus on the usage and demonstration of these enablers at MLLs and NMS cases, including the testing and user feedback for the tools developed.

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APPENDIX A: CODE REPOSITORIES

The source code for the GEMINI Data space can be found under

<https://gitlab.com/konnecta/projects/gemini/data-space>

This is a private repository, therefore please contact KONNECTA team to gain read-only access to it.

Similarly, the source code for the GEMINI BI Platform can be found under

<https://gitlab.com/konnecta/projects/gemini/bi-platform>

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